

Studies on Solutions of High Dielectric Constant. Part VI. Activity Coefficients of some Alkyl-substituted Ammonium Halides in Aqueous and Formamide Solutions

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In view of the abnormally high activity coefficients of tetra-alkylammonium iodides in aqueous solutions from E.M.F. measurements, reported by Devanathan and Fernando¹ and contradicted by Stokes², the work has been repeated to ascertain the correctness or otherwise of the freezing point data of Ebert and Lange³. The data now obtained are similar to those of Ebert and Lange and yield normal activity coefficients for tetra-alkylammonium halides in aqueous solutions. The work has been extended to solutions of these salts in formamide in which normal activity coefficients, less than 1, are obtained as in aqueous solutions.

The variation of $\gamma_{\pm}$ values with molality indicates strong ion-solvent interaction in spite of the large size of these tetra-alkylammonium ions. It is suggested that this interaction may be the filling up of spaces inside these 'hollow' ions by the solvent molecules which are held inside the ion by the positive charge on the nitrogen atom.

The abnormally high activity coefficients, reported by Devanathan and Fernando¹, for some tetra-alkylammonium iodides in water from E.M.F. measurements have drawn the attention of some prominent physical chemists and several interesting communications have appeared very recently on the subject. In the beginning these results were doubted and indeed from the freezing point depression measurements of Ebert and Lange³ on aqueous solutions of these salts, Stokes² obtained normal activity coefficients, quite in contrast to those obtained by Devanathan and Fernando¹. Stokes² also obtained similar normal activity coefficients, less than 1, from the isopiestic data of Bowler-Reed⁴ for these salts in aqueous solutions. Later, Bower and Robinson⁵ obtained activity coefficients, less than unity, from the isopiestic data of their own. More recently, Lindenbaum and Boyd⁶ came to similar conclusions from the isopiestic measurements.

On the other hand, the E.M.F. measurements of Bower and Robinson⁵ confirm the experimental results of Devanathan and Fernando¹. An explanation for the high values of the activity coefficients has been suggested by Frank⁷ with a remark for the further study of the problem.

When the curious results of Devanathan and Fernando were first reported, it was considered desirable to verify their findings by other methods like depression in the freezing point measurements. Although some data on these lines already exist in the literature, as pointed out earlier², it is necessary to redetermine the depressions in the freezing points of aqueous solutions of these salts in order to be definitely sure about the accuracy of the

1. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1962, 58, 784.
2. *Z. physical. Chem.*, 1928, 139, 584.
3. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, 59, 761.
4. Conway, "Electrochemical Data", 1962, p. 80.
5. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, 59, 1717.
6. *J. Phys. Chem.* 1964, 68, 911.
7. *Ibid.*, 1963, 67, 1654.

existing data in view of the contradictory results on the activity coefficients. It was also considered desirable to extend the work to solutions of these salts in formamide to observe the effect of the change of the solvent on the activity coefficients of these salts. Besides, the study of some trialkyl- and tetra-mixed alkylammonium halides to examine the effect of incomplete substitution has been made.

EXPERIMENTAL

The B.D.H.. C.P. grade salts were recrystallised from ethanolic solution and dried. The freezing point depressions were measured in the usual manner, both in aqueous and formamide solutions. In handling solutions in formamide, precautions were taken to keep the solutions protected from the atmospheric moisture. This was achieved by attaching a wide tube, filled with H_2SO_4 (conc.), to the measuring tube, in which the experimental solution was kept, through a side tube. Without this precaution, fluctuation in the freezing point depressions or rather a continuous decrease in the freezing points was observed. Formamide was purified in the usual manner. Freezing point of every sample of the solvent was determined. The values of the depressions in the F.P. (Tables I and II) are the mean of three readings which are reproducible within $\pm 0.002^\circ$.

TABLE I

Solvent = water.

m.	Δt_f .	$\gamma_{\pm}$.	m.	Δt_f .	$\gamma_{\pm}$.
A. $(CH_3)_5NHI$.					
0.1002	0.340	0.819	0.4000	1.195	0.608
0.1995	0.640	0.719	0.5017	1.470	0.566
0.2995	0.910	0.645	0.5994	1.740	0.542
B. $(C_2H_5)_3NHCl$.					
0.1015	0.340	0.788	0.2999	0.940	0.840
0.1505	0.500	0.749	0.4007	1.220	0.804
0.2006	0.650	0.707	0.5008	1.500	0.672
0.2505	0.800	0.678	..	..	..
C. $(CH_3)_3NC_6H_5I$.					
0.0886	0.330	0.795	0.4003	1.120	0.587
0.2008	0.610	0.664	0.4999	1.390	0.508
0.2962	0.860	0.593	..	..	..

From the F.P. depressions, Δt_f 's, the values of the factor 'j' of the equation:

$$j = 1 - \frac{\Delta t_f}{v.m. K_f}$$

were determined for each concentration. Here v denotes the number of ions in which the

electrolyte dissociates and K_f , the molal depression constant (for water 1.863° and for formamide 3.560°; cf. Dawson and Griffith⁶). From the values of j at different concentrations, j/m (m being the molal concentration) was obtained. The corresponding mean molal activity coefficients were then obtained from the usual graphical integration of the equation:

$$\ln \gamma_{\pm} = - \int_0^m \frac{j}{m} dm - j.$$

TABLE II

m .	Δt_f .	$\gamma_{\pm}$.	m .	Δt_f .	$\gamma_{\pm}$.
A. $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NI}$.					
0.0490	0.315	0.799	0.0971	0.600	0.711
0.0747	0.460	0.733	..	..	..
B. $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{NBr}$.					
0.1006	0.670	0.874	0.4032	2.580	0.744
0.1989	1.300	0.809	0.4984	3.180	0.725
0.3057	1.940	0.759	..	..	..
C. $(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_4\text{NI}$.					
0.1004	0.650	0.820	0.4057	2.270	0.586
0.2010	1.215	0.710	0.5042	2.780	0.551
0.3016	1.740	0.638	..	..	..
D. $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{NHI}$.					
0.1008	0.855	0.893	0.4003	2.320	0.624
0.2010	1.240	0.736	0.5027	2.640	0.585
0.3024	1.780	0.665	..	..	..
E. $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{NHCl}$.					
0.1005	0.680	0.849	0.4043	2.360	0.640
0.2018	1.250	0.752	0.5009	2.920	0.617
0.3014	1.800	0.687	..	..	..
F. $(\text{OH}_2)_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NI}$.					
0.0980	0.635	0.806	0.3001	1.740	0.628
0.1990	1.195	0.695	0.4037	2.280	0.581

The freezing point depressions as well as the mean molal activity coefficients, $\gamma_{\pm}$, obtained from the above procedure, are recorded in Tables I and II. Data on the aqueous solutions of the symmetrically substituted tetra-alkylammonium salts have been omitted as these are very much similar to those of Ebert and Lange⁷.

DISCUSSION

From Tables I and II, so far as the F.P. method is concerned, activity coefficients appear to be less than unity both in aqueous and in formamide solutions. Also no abnormality is noticed in the unsymmetrically substituted halides. Similar results on the activity coefficients of halides of Li, Na, K, Rb, and Cs in formamide, from the freezing point depression measurements, have been reported by Vasenko⁹. The values of $\gamma_{\pm}$, shown in the tables, appear to be slightly higher in formamide than those in water at the corresponding concentrations. Thus the isopiestic⁵⁻⁶ and the F.P. depression data on aqueous and formamide solutions lead to normal activity coefficients. On the other hand, the E.M.F. measurements in aqueous solutions seem to provide high activity coefficients. Inevitable conclusion is that either the cell reaction, proposed by Devanathan and Fernando¹, is questionable⁷ and needs modification or there is some trouble at the liquid junction.

An interesting approach to explain away these difficulties has been suggested by Frank⁷. According to him the cell set-up by Devanathan and Fernando actually measures the ratio of the activity coefficients of the single iodide ions in the two solutions and not the ratio of the mean activity coefficients, as has been assumed by Devanathan and Fernando¹. This may explain the apparent anomaly between the results obtained from the F.P. depression and those from E.M.F. measurements. All the same, the ratio: $\gamma_{I^{-}(aq)} / \gamma_{I^{-}(m)}$, is abnormally high. Frank⁷ has qualitatively suggested an explanation, depending on the structure-breaking effect of the K^{+} ion and the structure-promoting effect of the R_4N^{+} on the tetrahedral structure of water. This explanation needs further examination before it can be accepted. We propose to examine this question in our laboratory.

Some interesting and at the same time disturbing conclusions can be drawn from the calculations, similar to those of Frank, on the individual ion-activity in aqueous HCl solutions. The influence of solvation on the single-ion activity coefficient has been examined by Robinson and Stokes¹⁰ and Bjerrum¹¹. According to them, the single-ion activity coefficient can be expressed as

$$\ln \gamma_{+} = \frac{3h_{+} + h_{-} - 2}{55.51} m \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

and

$$\ln \gamma_{-} = \frac{3h_{-} + h_{+} - 2}{55.51} m \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

The terms used have their usual significance. If one assumes with others¹⁰ that the hydra-

9. *Zhur. Fiz. Khim.*, 1947, 21, 361; 1948, 22, 989.

10. "Electrolyte Solutions", Butterworths Publication, London, 1959, pp. 238-50.

11. *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1920, 109, 275.

tion number 'h', of any one of the tetra-alkylammonium ions, R_4N^+ , is low and very likely zero* and that of K^+ ion about two, relation (ii) leads to

$$\ln \gamma_{I^-(R_4N)} = \frac{3h_- + 0 - 2}{55.51} m = \frac{3h_- - 2}{55.51} m \quad \dots \quad (iii)$$

and

$$\ln \gamma_{I^-(K)} = \frac{3h_- + 2 - 2}{55.51} m = \frac{3h_-}{55.51} m \quad \dots \quad (iv)$$

At $m = 0.1$, the relations (ii) and (iv) provide

$$\log \frac{\gamma_{I^-(R_4N)}}{\gamma_{I^-(K)}} = \frac{-0.2}{2.303 \times 55.51} = \bar{1}.9984$$

Whence

$$\frac{\gamma_{I^-(R_4N)}}{\gamma_{I^-(K)}} = 0.9983 \approx 1.$$

This ratio is perfectly normal. The normal ratio poses a number of problems. Firstly, the results of Devanathan and Fernando¹ may be questionable, but these have already been verified. Secondly, the interpretation of the cell reaction and the explanation for the high values of the activity coefficients, reported by Frank², may be doubtful. Further work is obviously necessary to settle these questions. Although Frank has dismissed the liquid junction as the possible cause of the high E.M.F., leading to high activity coefficient ratios, it may not be unreasonable to suggest that the large difference in the mobilities of R_4N^+ ions and ions like K^+ or Cl^- may be the real cause of the trouble.

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* Although these ions are usually assumed to be unsolvated, some kind of ion-solvent interaction has to be acknowledged to explain their abnormal behaviour in solution. It has been found here that the $\log \gamma_{\pm}$ vs. $\sqrt{m}$ curves for all the halides of these ions, both in aqueous and formamide solutions, have large negative deviations from the theoretical slopes. This indicates some kind of ion-solvent interaction, not usually comprehensible for such large ions. Frank² proposes that the water-hating alkyl chains of these ions encourage tetrahedral-structure formation around the ions. Eley suggests the tightening of the hydrogen bonds of water molecules around the ions (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1934, 35, 1421; *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, 24, 218). One of the present authors (R.G.) has suggested (this issue, p. 209) that the solvent molecules get into the vacant spaces between the alkyl chains attached tetrahedrally to the central positively charged nitrogen atom. These ions do not have inert-gas structure and are "hollow". The positive charge on the nitrogen atom also holds the 'intruding' solvent molecules in place by electrostatic attraction. Rotation of the ions will be very slow on account of their large unwieldy size and of the steric effect of the long alkyl chains and so the solvent molecules can easily get inside the ions. The results of Wen-Yang Wen and Shuji Sato (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, 68, 2699) on the partial ionic volumes of these ions as well as the other properties of these ions appear to support this concept.